

FP7 POST-GRANT OPEN ACCESS PILOT, FINAL REPORT

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	Name	Organisation	Date
From	Gwen Franck	LIBER	06/2018
Edited by	Simone Sacchi	LIBER	
	Astrid Verheusen		
	Vasso Kalaitzi		
	Ilaria Fava	UGOE	
	Saskia De Vries	SURF	
	Frank Manista	JISC	
Reviewed by	Natalia Manola	UoA	
Approved by			
For delivery	Mike Chatzopoulos	UoA	

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Acronyms

APC	Article Processing Charge
BPC	Book Processing Charge

Publishable Summary

FINAL REPORT OF THE FP7 POST-GRANT OPEN ACCESS PILOT

This report contains an overview of all activities conducted of all activities undertaken by OpenAIRE2020 WP5.

It contains a summary of the FP7 Post-Grant Open Access Pilot, which is largely based on D 5.4 (Second periodic report on APC uptake and metrics, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1298562>), updated with the data described in MS 72 (Final periodic report on APC uptake and metrics) which deals with the remaining data processed during the extension period (April 30th, 2017 until February 28th, 2018) and, finally, any data processed after the end of the extension period.

It provides an analysis of the workflows of the pre-payment agreements made with several open access publishers and with two research libraries, and a short overview of the economic study executed by Research Consulting 'Towards a competitive and sustainable open access publishing market in Europe'.

The Pilot organized three workshops and two internal meetings. A short report on each of these meetings are also included here. Over the duration of the Pilot, several online trainings and webinars were also given, of which the recordings and slides are listed here as well.

Finally, it also contains an overview of the activities undertaken as part of the alternative funding mechanism workline – two funding rounds of € 200 000 each, through which in total 17 non-author fee based publishing platforms were funded in order to conduct technical improvement, research into suitable business models, and into sustainability and scalability of their platform. As the deadline for reporting of the second round of this funding is June 30th, 2018, the Zenodo file of this deliverable will receive an update once all reporting has been completed.

1 | POST-GRANT OPEN ACCESS PILOT: STATISTICS

Following an intensive consultation exercise in order to put together a consensus set of policy guidelines for this EC FP7 Post-Grant Open Access Pilot, <https://www.openaire.eu/postgrantoapilot>, the funding initiative was actually launched at the end of May 2015 with the release of the system at <https://postgrantoapilot.openaire.eu/>.

The Pilot, originally intended to end on April 30th, 2017 has been granted a 10 month extension until end of February 2018. The data in this report deals with all submissions from May 2015 until the final submission deadline on February 28th, 2018 and includes data about existing submissions that have been processed during March 2018. Some data, however, has not been completely processed yet. When possible, this report completed missing information based on existing averages and pre-reported data. As none of these pending data significantly differs from the data provided in the system, we do not believe that this will influence the statistical analysis below, although individual numbers (such as number of articles funded per publisher) might change a little bit.

The datasets on which this report is based are available on Zenodo ([DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.998041](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.998041)). We explicitly invite interested parties to conduct their own analysis based on **the original dataset**. It is also possible to download a csv with all data directly from the Pilot website <https://postgrantoapilot.openaire.eu>.

1.1 First Period (May 2015 – April 2017)

Full blogpost: <https://blogs.openaire.eu/?p=2312>

The FP7 Post-Grant Open Access Pilot has made an analysis of the results of the first 'period' of the Pilot – from May 2015 until April 30th 2017 – in other words, this is the overview of all activity for the Pilot within the 2-year timeframe it was originally intended for.

The dataset it is based on is extracted from the statistics module on the Pilot website – edited, corrected and augmented manually with data obtained externally such as the data from the pre-payment agreements with selected publishers – in order to give a complete overview. [This dataset is available on Zenodo \(doi:10.5281/zenodo.998041\)](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.998041). 4 months into the extension, some of the numbers will already be outdated, but we believe that the trends and conclusions discussed here are still valid, and that they can be used for prediction and projection until the end of the Pilot extension (in February 2018).

On April 30, 2017 a total amount of ca. € 1 497 000 has been spent on a total of 857 publications. The average author fee paid is € 1747 – with an average of € 1 477 for articles and € 5 364 for monographs. Both averages are well below the imposed funding caps of € 2 000 for articles and € 6 000 for monographs.

The Pilot has funded 59 monographs and 1 conference proceeding, 11 book chapters and 786 articles in full open access journals (the Pilot does not fund publications in so-called hybrid journals, i.e. journals that offer open access for certain articles while the journal as a whole remains subscription based).

1.1.1 Countries, journals and publishers

The countries with the highest number of funded requests are Spain and the UK, each at 128 publications. Italy, Germany and the Netherlands follow. In total, we have received requests from 36 countries.

Below, you can see the list of the most popular journals and book publishers with the average author fees paid. There have been two different funding caps: one for article processing charges, set at € 2 000 and one for book processing charges, set at € 6 000. However, the numbers below do not represent the huge differences between fees charged – not only to these vary per publisher, the fees can even vary within the same journal as discounts are often applied (on individual or institutional basis). For any analysis, averages need to be dealt with carefully. Especially for journal articles, we should also take into account the median value (which is € 1 4 13 for articles)

Journal	Nr of publications funded	Publisher	Average APC paid
Scientific Reports	91	Nature Publishing Group	€ 1179
PLoS ONE	73	Public Library of Science (PLoS)	€ 1333
Nature Communications	34	Springer Nature	€ 1996
Sensors	22	MDPI AG	€ 1601
Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*	21	Copernicus GmbH	€ 1472
Optics Express	17	Optical Society of America	€ 1838
Biogeosciences*	16	Copernicus GmbH	€ 1308
Frontiers in Plant Science	14	Frontiers Media SA	€ 1869
BMC Genomics*	13	BioMedCentral	€ 1716
Frontiers in Microbiology	11	Frontiers Media SA	€ 1625

TABLE 1: JOURNAL PUBLISHERS FIRST PERIOD (MAY 2015-APRIL 2017)

Out of the 59 books and monographs published, 47 were with the following publishers:

Book Publisher	Nr of publications funded	Average BPC paid
River Publishers	22	€ 6 000
InTech	10	€ 1 541
Ubiquity Press	8	€ 3 261
Springer	7	€ 5 260

TABLE 2: TABLE 1: MONOGRAPHS 1ST PERIOD (MAY 2015-APRIL 2017)

1.1.2 Average and median charges

Via the site, 672 articles in full Open Access Journals have been funded, for a total of € 980 012, 43. This leads to an average APC of € 1 458 and a median APC that is even lower, at € 1 413. The lowest APC funded was € 209. The 114 articles that have been funded via the pre-payment agreements with the publishers BMC, BMJ, Copernicus and Wiley have been funded for a total of € 180 958, 5. Part of the agreement was that these publishers would apply a discounted APC. The average APCs for these publishers is as follows: Wiley € 1 411, BMC € 1 712, BMJ € 1 684 and Copernicus € 1 405. Adding these numbers to the submitted data, we arrive at a total of € 1 160 970, 93 spent on 786 (672 + 114) publications, leading to an average of €1 477 per publication.

	Number	Average author fee paid	Total fees paid
Articles	786	€ 1 477	€ 1 160 971
Monographs	59	€ 5 364	€ 316 449
Total	845	€ 1 747	€ 1 496 811

TABLE 3: OVERVIEW FIRST PERIOD (MAY 2015-APRIL 2017)

1.1.3 Some remarks and conclusions for the first period:

There is a dedicated statistics site on the website which can be used for basic and combined extractions of the data generated by the system. However, this does not reflect fully the complicated combination of factors that can influence the analysis of author fees paid.

A first point to notice is that this data is based on information ingested in the system and therefore also copies their errors – whenever a submitter did not make use of the pre-filled information (such as publisher or institution information), this can influence the outputs as some inputs are classified separately while essentially they are identical. For proper analysis, this needed manual editing.

Another disturbing factor can be the conversion of other currencies to €. Especially with USD and GBP being rather volatile in the first quarter of 2017, the cap of € 2 000 was sometimes exceeded when converting.

A third factor to take into account is the different statuses of the publications. Although the Pilot encourages authors to submit only after acceptance (and thus the generation of an invoice), researchers often like to ‘play safe’ and use the submitting system as a manner of verification to check whether their publication or journal is actually eligible – or to ensure that their publication is one of the three publications allowed per project. This results in a lot of ‘noise’ in the dataset extracted from the system – with plenty of duplicates, incomplete requests and submissions without invoice. This often leads to inconsistent data, for example when one wants to count the number of publications per institution.

We can safely say that the average author fee for articles (APC) at € 1 477 lies well below our funding cap of € 2 000. The median, at € 1 413, is even lower.

The five countries with the highest uptake are UK, Netherlands, Germany, Italy and Spain. Although it is difficult to point to one cause for this, it is safe to assume that this can be explained either because there is already a high awareness of author fee reimbursement policies (for example in UK and NL), or because there has been intensive promotion of the Pilot (such as in Spain). Of course, country population and number of eligible FP7 projects coordinated play a role as well

The most controversial clause in the Pilot conditions is without a doubt the 'no hybrids' clause. This clause is not only contested by those publishers who have a lot of hybrid journals in their portfolios, but also by researchers who often either have no idea whether their journal of choice is a hybrid or are used to their hybrid publications being funded by other funders. However, it is the Pilot administration subjective experience that, if explained properly, this clause is not problematic anymore

Prepayment agreements with publishers and block grants with libraries can lead to a significant increase in funding, as this takes away most of the administrative burden from the researcher. However, it is to be noted that the current workflows in place, while in all probability are rather efficient in detecting eligible publications, are suboptimal when it comes to statistical analysis.

It is important to stress to potential beneficiaries that the support provided via this Pilot is indeed a Pilot and cannot be considered as a structural support mechanism. We have seen a recent influx of questions from H2020 projects who want to know whether they can get support – there is low awareness of the fact that Open Access publishing costs are to be included in the budget of these projects.

1.2 Extension (April 2017 – February 2018) and final results for the entire duration

Full blog post: <https://blogs.openaire.eu/?p=2917>

The Pilot, originally intended to end on April 30th 2017, had been granted a 10 month extension and has come to an end in February 2018.

During this period, an additional 469 publications have been processed through the portal (so, excluding the ones supported through the prepayment agreements), leading to a total of 1131 publications funded.

As no submissions have been accepted after 28th February 2018, we can now calculate the final numbers. However, as even at the end of the Pilot a couple of submissions are still being dealt with (because of administrative issues with invoices from the submitters' side), the numbers communicated below can still change a little bit – not influencing our general statistical conclusions however.

On a total budget of € 4 000 000 000, approximately € 2 250 000 has been spent on paying author fees.

In total, the Pilot has funded **1 323 publications: 1 232 articles, 71 monographs, 18 book chapters and 2 conference proceedings (this includes the publications processed via the pre-payment agreements).**

The average author fee for articles processed is € 1 474 and the median fee is € 1446.

1.2.1 Detailed statistical analysis

In total, 1323 publications have been approved and paid for, or are being processed at the writing of this report. These publications have been submitted directly through the portal or via the publishers and library prepayment funds. 312 requests have never been completed, and 388 request have been rejected by the Pilot administration. The Pilot has processed 1232 articles, 71 monographs, 18 book chapters and 2 conference proceedings.

After a slow start in the first months of the Pilot, the average number of requests per month increased to an average of 53 per month, with predictable lows during the holiday months and peaks following dissemination efforts by the Pilot administration and OpenAIRE NOADs and near the end of both the official first closing date (April 30th 2017) and the final closing date (after the extension period) February 28th 2018.

FIGURE 1: FUNDING REQUESTS PER MONTH (ENTIRE DURATION OF PILOT)

1.2.2 Distribution by country

The country data are based on the location of the submitter of the funding request. This is often, but not necessarily, the corresponding author – sometimes a submission happened by the project coordinator. The ‘per country’ statistic therefore offers a valuable insight on where the Pilot dissemination efforts might have worked best, but is mainly a reflection of the country population and number of FP7 publications. The Pilot processed applications from 42 countries, with the almost half of all applications coming from United Kingdom, Spain, Italy and Germany.

As country of origin of the submitting author has not been included in the data requested from the publishers in the pre-payment agreements, the 77 publications that have not been ingested into the system at the moment of writing this report (see **Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden.**) are

not included in these statistics, but there is no reason to expect a big impact on the overall distribution shown below.

United Kingdom	185	Poland	6
Spain	158	Lithuania	5
Italy	131	Czech Republic	4
Germany	121	Croatia	3
Netherlands	87	Russian Federation	3
France	60	South Africa	3
Greece	39	Australia	2
Switzerland	38	Cyprus	2
Austria	37	Tanzania (United Republic of)	2
Ireland	30	United States	2
Sweden	30	Bulgaria	1
Belgium	26	Burkina Faso	1
Denmark	25	Estonia	1
Finland	24	Iceland	1
Hungary	18	India	1
Israel	18	Latvia	1
Portugal	17	Luxembourg	1
Serbia	14	Mexico	1
Norway	13	Slovakia	1
Slovenia	13	Ukraine	1
Turkey	11		

TABLE 4: DISTRIBUTION OF REQUESTS PER COUNTRY OF SUBMITTER

1.2.3 Journals

From the start, it has been a crucial element of the FP7 Open Access Fund that only 'full Open Access' journals will be supported. The so-called 'hybrid' journals, i.e. journals that offer an Open

Access option on article basis but remain subscription based as a whole, do not qualify for support from this fund. Whether a journal is a full Open Access one was manually checked by the Pilot administration – via a cross-check with Directory of Open Access Journals¹ and, if necessary, a check on the journal home page. The fact that a journal was hybrid, was the main reason for rejection of a submission – and it is also the subject of most disputes with authors as they are often not aware of a)what a hybrid journal is and b)what the status of their journal is or c)they are used to funders who do support hybrid (namely in UK and NL). This explains the relatively low amount of articles published with large publishers who offer well known but hybrid Open Access Journals.

In total (approximately) € 1 883 000 has been spent on article processing fees, € 376 000 on book processing fees and € 22 431 on conference proceedings and book chapters, leading to a total of (approximately) € 2 300 000 spent. These figures include the numbers reported by the publishers participating in the pre-payment agreements and might be different than the ones shown on the Pilot website as not all this data has been ingested at the moment of writing (April 2018).

Below are listed the most popular journals and publishers, together with the average author fees paid. A couple of observations need to be made here:

- Author fees can vary highly, even for the same journal. Several factors can influence this: whether the institution has a discount agreement with the publisher, the location of the author requesting the fee. OpenAIRE also has agreements with certain publishers in order to apply a discount. In some cases, the publisher also simply lowered the author fee requested to stay below our funding caps.
- Invoices could be issued in the currency of choice, but the statistics record the converted amount in EUR. Volatile currencies such as GBP and USD can result in different fees in EUR for the same amount in the original currency
- When the original author fee exceeded our funding cap of €2000 for journal articles or €6000 for monographs we asked the submitted to provide either a split invoice or a request for reimbursement by the institution for no more than the amount allowed. The figures below do not record original author fees above the funding caps. The original fees requested can be consulted in the full dataset.

In general, it’s useful to remark here that these numbers are in any case an approximation: currency conversion and banking fees might mean that in total a slightly larger amount will have been spent. Again, we believe the statistical trends to be robust enough not be influenced by these fluctuations.

At the end the Pilot, a total of 301 journals have had at least one article supported. For a full overview, we refer to the dataset available on Zenodo. 41 journals have had five or more articles supported. Again, the 77 publications from the pre-payment agreements are not included in this overview. We believe that the relative weight of each journal will not be influenced by the one or two additional publications that might be added to their tally.

Journal	ISSN	Number of publications	Average APC in EUR
Scientific Reports	2045-2322	136	1216
PLoS ONE	1932-6203	97	1317

¹ www.doaj.org – DOAJ does not index hybrid open access journals and is therefore a reliable though not exhaustive source

Nature Communications	2041-1723	51	1997
Sensors	1424-8220	28	1569
Optics Express	1094-4087	23	1808
Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics	1680-7324	22	1516
Frontiers in Plant Science	1664-462X	21	1881
Frontiers in Psychology	1664-1078	15	1667
Biogeosciences	1726-4170,1726-4189	14	1266
Frontiers in Microbiology	1664-302X	14	1628
Cell Reports	2211-1247	12	1991
Ecology and Evolution	2045-7758	11	1295
Energies	1996-1073	11	1215
Environmental Research Letters	1748-9326	11	1506
BMC Genomics	1471-2164	11	1733
New Journal of Physics	1367-2630	9	1297
PLoS Computational Biology	1553-734X,1553-7358	8	1958
Sustainability	2071-1050	8	1058
BMC Bioinformatics	1471-2105	7	1463
Frontiers in Immunology	1664-3224	7	1791
Frontiers in Marine Science	2296-7745,2296-7745	7	1483
PLoS Genetics	1553-7390,1553-7404	7	1983
Ecology and Society	1708-3087	6	1133
Frontiers in Human Neuroscience	1662-5161	6	1661
Health Research Policy and Systems	1478-4505	6	1799
Oncotarget	1949-2553	6	1985
Remote Sensing	2072-4292	6	1236
Science Advances	2375-2548	6	1785

Stem Cell Research	1873-5061,1876-7753	6	878
BMJ Global Health	2059-7908	5	1812
BMJ Open	2044-6055	5	1521
ChemistryOpen	2191-1363	5	1632
Forests	1999-4907	5	989
Frontiers in Neuroscience	1662-5129	5	1533
Frontiers in Physiology	1662-4548,1662-453X	5	1504
Implementation Science	1748-5908	5	1713
International Journal of Molecular Sciences	1422-0067	5	1433
Materials	1996-1943	5	1273
Molecules	1420-3049	5	1638
PeerJ	2167-8359	5	786
Physical Review X	2160-3308	5	1810

TABLE 5: JOURNALS WITH 5 OR MORE PUBLICATIONS SUPPORTED BY THE PILOT AND THE AVERAGE APC PAID

It is interesting to note that the average article processing charge of € 1474 and the median value of € 1446 is well below the funding cap of €2000. The relatively high amount of fees between €2000 and €2300 are all fees that stayed below the cap at submission stage (otherwise the system would not have accepted them) but came out slightly higher because of currency conversions. The lowest fee paid was €180.

FIGURE 2: DISTRIBUTION OF AUTHOR FEES PAID (JOURNALS) IN EUR

1.2.4 Publishers

The table below lists the most popular publishers funded by the Pilot (including the publications processed through the prepayment agreements).

Publisher	Publications
Springer International Publishing	256
Public Library of Science (PLoS)	123
Frontiers Media SA	113
Copernicus GmbH	111
MDPI AG	106
BioMed Central (part of Springer)	106
Wiley-Blackwell	44
Elsevier BV	42
The Optical Society	27
IOP Publishing	23
River Publishers	23
Hindawi Publishing Corporation	22
Intech	17
BMJ Journals	15
Oxford University Press (OUP)	11

Nature Publishing Group	9
Ubiquity Press, Ltd.	9
Institute of Electrical & Electronics Engineers (IEEE)	7
AIP Publishing	6
Impact Journals, LLC	6

TABLE 6: NUMBER OF PUBLICATIONS PER PUBLISHER

A couple of observations:

- Many publishers are known under different names and aliases, and because of take-overs and mergers the data sometimes shows the same journal as being published by different publishers (such as the BioMedCentral, who are sometimes listed as published by BMC and sometimes as published by Springer. When possible, the Pilot administration has tried to manually edit this for statistical purposes, but as shown in the table below sometimes considered it opportune to treat the original publishers as different entities. The original dataset lists the publishers as entered by the author in the system.
- The Pilot has actively engaged with several publishers to raise awareness about the Pilot and even to put pre-payment agreements in place (as was the case for BioMedCentral, BMJ, Wiley, Copernicus and Ubiquity Press). Even some publishers who did not have a formal prepayment agreement actively engaged with the Pilot to identify potential beneficiaries (such as River Publishers).

TABLE 7: 20 MOST POPULAR PUBLISHERS

1.2.5 Books and book chapters, conference proceedings

The Pilot has funded 71 books, 18 book chapters and 2 conference proceedings. The following publishers have had more than one publication funded.

The first time a funding request arrived for publishing a monograph, book chapter edited volume or conference proceedings with a publisher that hadn't been funded before, a list of five questions was sent out to the book author/editor so that they're jointly answered by the author and the publisher. These technical requirements needed to be met in order for a funding request for a book to be accepted.

- Will a DOI be provided to the book upon publication?
- Will the FP7 project be acknowledged in the book?
- What CC licence will the book be published under?
- The policy guidelines for this funding initiative mention the requirement to make available a text-minable version (ideally an XML version) besides the standard PDF one. For books, Epub could be an alternative to XML, but some text-minable version should be made available.
- There is a requirement in the guidelines to have the final version of the funded output deposited in an OpenAIRE-compliant repository. Could we confirm if the publisher is able to do this on its own, and otherwise, if there would be any problem with our depositing it ourselves?

River Publishers	23
InTech	17
Ubiquity Press, Ltd.	10
Springer International Publishing	4
Brill	3
Springer	3
Ljubljana University Press	3
Routledge	2
Manchester University Press	2
Silva Slovenica Publishing Centre, Slovenian Forestry Institute	2

TABLE 8: BOOK PUBLISHERS WITH TWO OR MORE PUBLICATIONS FUNDED BY THE PILOT

1.2.6 Projects

In total, 810 FP7 projects have submitted one or more request. 79 projects have depleted their available funds completely by having 3 publications approved, 154 have 2 publications funded. In case of multiple submissions per project which would lead to exceeding this limit of 3 publications, the project coordinator was contacted in order to prioritize their submissions. However, 4 projects have 5 publications funded. Though technically impossible as the system gave an automatic rejection note once the limit of 3 publications had been reached, this can be attributed to publications belonging to the same projects being simultaneously processed through the system and via the pre-payment agreements. As reporting on these agreements happened at interval levels, these errors could not be avoided and the Pilot has decided not to retract the funding.

1.2.7 Licensing and other technical requirements: compliance

Although the Pilot encouraged authors to (when not standardly offered) ask for a CC BY or CC BY-SA – the most open Creative Commons licenses – but this was not actively enforced. 123 articles are licensed CC BY. 3 publications have the ‘non-commercial’ clause (CC BY-NC) or even CC BY—NC-ND, which are not considered ‘open’ licenses. However, some random samples of publications not licensed explicitly in the metadata show that the publication is de facto licensed as CC BY. At the very least, a majority of authors retained their author rights.

Another requirement for compliance was that a permanent identifier (such as a doi) should be assigned to the publication. This could also be added afterwards. At the moment of writing this report, 150 publications do not have a doi assigned, which means that over 90% of submissions are compliant with this rule. 270 publications have been registered in an OpenAIRE compliant

repository (and are thus harvested by OpenAIRE), but in reality this number is probably a lot higher, as this was not an obligatory field and a lot of depositing happens post-publication.

1.2.8 Distribution per Programme Area

FP7 projects are categorized under several areas. The Pilot has recorded the number of publications per programme area.

PEOPLE	312
ERC	161
HEALTH	160
ICT	155
ENV	84
KBBE	76
NMP	44
SME	23
INFRA	23
REGPOT	22
TPT	15
ENERGY	14
SPA	12
SSH	12
SP1-JTI	10
SEC	6
SiS	4
INCO	2
Fission	1
REGIONS	1

TABLE 9: FUNDED PUBLICATIONS PER PROGRAMME AREA

1.3 Remaining Data

Although the Pilot officially closed on February 28th, 2018, there are still a couple of publications 'pending' because the accounting process has not been finalised. When data could be estimated, it has already been added to the analysis but they might not be visible in the statistical module of the [Pilot](#) website. As none of this pending data significantly differs from the data provided in the system, we do not believe that this will have an influence on the statistical analysis, although

individual numbers (such as number of articles funded per publisher) might change a little bit. As the final data will be processed, we will provide an updated version of the dataset attached to the same Zenodo record.

1.4 General conclusions about the reimbursements

Extension Period: With an additional 469 publications published in the final 10 months of the Pilot (the extension period), allowing for an extension period has definitely proven to be an appropriate decision.

Budget: with a total spending of approx. € 2 250 000 on 1323 publications the Pilot has been overbudgeted. But as has been indicated, estimating the popularity of the Pilot was a difficult exercise to begin with. We hope that the average and median amounts indicated in this final report will prove a useful tool to calculate any future funding.

Medians and averages: with median and average values for article processing charges well below our funding cap of € 2 000, the Pilot has proven that setting standards at funder level can have a positive influence on APC height.

No hybrids: although the ‘no hybrid’ policy caused some frustration for researchers who are used to getting hybrid funding at other funders, the Pilot took great care to explain why hybrids were not allowed. In fact, most researchers were unaware what the term means, and also had difficulty to identify their journal of choice as ‘hybrid’ (the fact that most publishers are deliberately vague about this, using terms as ‘open choice’, ‘open access option’ etc does not help). If anything this shows that more education about different open access options is a necessity.

Projects reached: the project has reached a little over 800 projects. The eligibility window shifted as the Pilot progressed (at the moment of submission, the project needed to have ended but not more than two years ago), so it is not possible to calculate the actual reach of the Pilot. As the majority of projects has only used 1 of the available 3 funding slots, there might have been some room for increased dissemination at project level.

Pilot not Policy: the fact that this Pilot was not a structural support mechanism caused a lot of frustration. The Pilot administration received a lot of complaints about funding not being allowed after the Pilot end date – and a lot of requests to establish a permanent fund at European level for author fee payment.

Licensing: although the use of open licenses was encouraged (and even requested when entering agreements with monograph publishers), this was not actively enforced. Random checks of licensing information showed that correct and open licensing is still an issue – mostly because the licensing information was not displayed correctly in the metadata or could not be extracted from it. It was beyond the Pilot administration capacity to manually check and correct every entry.

Workflows: the workflow was, perhaps necessarily, rather complicated. Especially the invoicing procedure caused a lot of delays and frustrations. Only a small minority of submissions could be approved without adjustment of the invoice. People did not understand that they needed to ask the publisher to address the invoice to Athena Research Centre (who handled the accounting) or that, in the case of a reimbursement to be made at institutional level, that ARC needed both the original invoice and a request for reimbursement. This often led to long and complicated e-mail

conversations including the pilot administration, the pilot accounting, the researcher, the publisher and the institution's administrative department, resulting in delays of payment.

Technical issues: the Pilot infrastructure encountered some technical issues that caused additional frustration and delays. One major technical failure caused the Pilot website to be unusable for almost 6 weeks, right at the start of the extension period.

Dissemination: the role of OpenAIRE NOADs has been essential in this. Dissemination efforts by individual NOADs led to small increases in submissions stemming from that NOADs country, as did centralized presentations by the Pilot administration. However, there is no evidence that project officers or project coordinators actively distributed information about the Pilot, so perhaps more effort should have been made there.

2 | PREPAYMENT AGREEMENTS

2.1 With Publishers

The Pilot has pre-payment agreements in place with 5 publishers, namely BioMedCentral, BMJ, Copernicus, Ubiquity Press (in a later stage) and Wiley-Blackwell. In the case of Copernicus and BioMedCentral the funds have been topped up at the end of 2017, based on an estimate of potentially eligible publications for the remainder of the Pilot. In these cases, OpenAIRE has made funds available to the publisher directly, eliminating the need for submission through the portal.

The publisher identified potentially eligible publications, either through mining the publication metadata or by specifically requesting project information from the authors, and sent them to the pilot administration on a regular basis. After an eligibility check of the project (checking end date and number of publications already funded) the pilot administration let the publisher know whether the publication can be added to the fund. This data has been collected and manually ingested into the system.

At the end of the Pilot, 186 publications have been funded via these pre-payment agreements, with 14 publications still pending due to editorial reasons.

Of these 186 publications, 77 are not ingested into the system yet although these are already added to the statistical analysis of the Pilot. The numbers generated by the system can thus differ from the numbers reported in this report. An overview of these publications is added to the dataset available on Zenodo and these are already included in the statistical analysis offered in this report.

Block Grant	Total amount grants	Total amount spent (on April 12 2018)	Maximum amount spent including pending	Total number of publications funded
BioMedCentral	€ 170.000,00	€ 139.327,00	€ 155.907	82
BMJ	€ 20.000	€ 8.422	€ 8.422	5
Copernicus	€ 171.000	€ 119.220	€ 119.220	80
Wiley	€ 60.000	€ 19.489	€ 23.856	15
Ubiquity Press	TBC	€ 14892,33	€ 14892,33	4
TOTAL	€ 421.000,00	€ 316.155,00	€ 337.102	186

TABLE 10: PRE-PAYMENT AGREEMENTS PUBLISHERS

An additional 14 publications will be added to this bulk in the end, as some publishers reported some pending publications (i.e. accepted publications that had to undergo an additional review at the moment of the Pilot closing date). While these will be processed via the funds, they are not included in the statistics (the maximum amount for these publications is around € 35 000).

Although the data from these agreements will be included in the final datasets available on Zenodo, a separate dataset will be added exclusively compiling this information.

This system has huge benefits for the researchers, as the invoicing process can be skipped entirely. The publishers concerned have also agreed to apply a discount on the author fees charged.

2.2 With Libraries

As an experiment, the Pilot has engaged with two libraries to explore the feasibility of implementing a decentralized funding mechanism based on the transferring of 'block grants': Radboud University (€29 500) and University of Bielefeld (€15 000). The Pilot engaged with librarians from both universities in order to train them to internally promote the funding initiative and to recognize eligible publications. The librarian submitted on behalf of the researcher and takes care of the APC payment – deducting it from the block grant.

TABLE 11: LIBRARY BLOCK GRANTS OVERVIEW

Library	Block Grant	Amount spent	Number of publications
Radboud University (NL)	€ 29 5000	€ 14.250,96	10
Bielefeld University (GE)	€15 000	€ 24.942,63	15
Total		€ 39.194	25

2.3 General conclusions about the pre-payment agreements

Lack of adequate metadata: in a lot of cases, the metadata provided by authors and/or publishers is inadequate. As the pilot administration needs accurate project identification in order to assess eligibility, determining whether a publication acknowledges a certain project was often a complicated process

Researcher awareness: the publishers informed researchers when a project was flagged as eligible, but for that to happen the researcher needed to be aware to include funder information in the metadata

Processing method: the fact that the Pilot offered tailor-made evaluating and reporting procedures for each publisher had a significant impact on both speed with which the data could be processed and on the subsequent reporting. Some publishers submitted data via a dashboard, while others submitted spreadsheets or even contacted the Pilot administration for individual publications. Also, the timing of evaluation was often different: some publishers submitted data before acceptance of the publication, which made it difficult to identify publications actually funded (some approved articles have never been published). Uniform workflows, putting the responsibility of correct evaluation and reporting at the publisher's instead of the Pilot, would have made this easier.

Timing: some publications have been evaluated 2 or even 3 times by the Pilot: once or twice because one of the authors made a submission, and 1 because they were flagged by the publisher. The Pilot administration has aimed to deduplicate all entries, but as titles can change and doi's are not always assigned at the moment of submissions, duplicate entries could not entirely be excluded

Number of publications per project: due to these parallel systems some projects will have more than 3 publications funded. While the Pilot administration made an effort to check all eligible publications flagged by publishers against the system in order to avoid this, some projects will have reached their limit in our system while in parallel some approved publications in the publisher's systems had not been added to the system yet, resulting in more than 3 publications per project in the final data.

3 | REPORT AND ROADMAP: “TOWARDS A COMPETITIVE AND SUSTAINABLE OA MARKET IN EUROPE – A STUDY OF THE OPEN ACCESS MARKET AND POLICY ENVIRONMENT”.

3.1 REPORT

In October 2016, [Research Consulting](#), within the scope of the OpenAIRE Work Package dealing with the [FP7 Post Grant Open Access Pilot](#) (WP5) – lead by [LIBER](#) – was commissioned by OpenAIRE on behalf of the European Commission to undertake an economic analysis study of the Open Access publishing market: “Towards a Competitive and Sustainable OA Market in Europe – A Study of the Open Access Market and Policy Environment”.

The [report \(pdf\)](#) is accompanied by an [Annex \(pdf\)](#) which contains the mid-term evaluation of the [FP7 Post-Grant Open Access Pilot](#), organised by OpenAIRE.

Full blogpost: <https://blogs.openaire.eu/?p=1841>

Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.401029>

3.2 ROADMAP:

The Roadmap, which is partially based on the abovementioned report, on information and feedback gathered during the two workshops organised by the Pilot and on observations made by the Pilot administration for the duration of the Pilot, will be made available on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1304904>)

4 | WORKSHOPS, ONLINE TRAINING, HELPDESK AND DISSEMINATION

4.1 Workshops

4.1.1 LIBER Annual Conference 2015, London, UK

Full blogpost: <https://blogs.openaire.eu/?p=417>

A well-attended 3-hr FP7 Post-Grant Open Access Pilot workshop was held on June 24th at the University of London Senate House within the LIBER Annual Conference 2015. Over 60 attendees made it to the event, which was no small feat with five additional workshops being simultaneously held in a parallel session. A quick hand-raising survey at the start of the session showed attendees were mainly representing universities and research centres, with approximately one third of them being UK-based, another third Dutch and the remaining one from the rest of the countries.

The workshop was designed as an interactive event: different aspects of the Pilot were covered with brief presentations, at the end of which a discussion was held with the audience. Some of the areas covered (see workshop programme and presentations) were the following ones:

- Pilot policy guidelines, in order to make sure the requirements for collecting the funding were well understood.
- The very diverse research funding landscape across countries, which will impact on the way the Pilot is implemented. This key project element was addressed via a round table where representatives of institutions fitting into the different funding scenarios identified by the Pilot shared their views on how successfully Gold Open Access could be promoted and supported under such specific circumstances.
- The central system for collecting and processing funding requests for the Pilot: a demo video was screened showing the steps to submit a funding request via this central system developed by OpenAIRE.
- The Pilot dissemination strategy at institutional level. Some recommendations were delivered for effectively reaching out to eligible researchers and projects at institutions, with a presentation by the University of Glasgow explaining their own dissemination campaign.
- Publishers and the FP7 Post-Grant OA Pilot: the supporting role publishers are being asked to play in order to further disseminate the Pilot was described, together with the work the Pilot is carrying out to analyse the feasibility of implementing APC-equivalent funding for non-APC-based journals and platforms.

Numerous questions were asked during the session on topics such as the eligibility criteria, the right moment for submitting a funding request, the mechanisms for co-funding publishing OA costs where applicable, the role of institutions interested in implementing the Pilot or the impact of the initiative of ruling out funding for publications in hybrid journals.

The institutions initially involved in the Pilot kick-off which were able to attend the event were very active, taking part in different sessions and sharing their expertise on the Pilot implementation. UCL (Catherine Sharp), Uni Bielefeld (Dirk Pieper), U Patras (Fieroula Papadatou), the Hungarian Academy of Sciences (Andras Holl) and Radboud Universiteit Nijmegen (Saskia de Vries) were part of the round table about the miscellaneous funding landscape across Europe and its impact on the Pilot implementation, the University of Glasgow (Valerie McCutcheon) delivered the abovementioned presentation on strategies for Pilot dissemination at institutional level, and Radboud also contributed to the session on Publishers and the Pilot.

Following the workshop, the rate of user registrations in the central system experienced an upsurge. A month and a half after the system release, nearly 150 users have already registered in the system, with close to 50 institutions already having access to the funding request submission process from their Libraries or Research Offices.

4.1.2 On the road towards a sustainable open access publishing market, The Hague, April 2017

Full blog post: <https://blogs.openaire.eu/?p=1884>

On 20th April 2017, the ‘closing’ workshop of the FP7 Post-Grant Open Access Pilot, organised by LIBER, took place at the Royal Library in The Hague, Netherlands. ([as has recently been announced](#), the Pilot has been extended with another 10 months – so ‘closing workshop’ might not be that accurate of a description) 60 stakeholders assembled for this day-long workshop. While the morning session focused on the activities undertaken during the Pilot, the afternoon was reserved for a presentation of the [report “Towards a Competitive and Sustainable OA Market in Europe”](#) by Research Consulting and a break-out session intended to gather input for the Roadmap that will accompany this report.

[In the Pilot overview and results](#), Gwen Franck: LIBER Open Access Project Officer Gwen Franck presented some notable statistics from the Pilot up to now, basically an update of [this report](#). The presentation also focused on some lessons learnt:

We need to simplify procedures and create transparent workflows,

A majority of journals stays well below the set cap of 2000€ and the importance of actors such as research librarians as a catalyst to increase researcher awareness – both on Open Access in general and on the existence of funding streams such as this one.

As has been the case for all communications around the EC Open Access policies, targeting project coordinators at the start of projects also proves to be a very efficient way of communication.

After this, there was a panel discussion featuring two publishers ([Mark De Jongh, River Publishers](#), and [Xenia Van Edig, Copernicus Publishing](#)) and one librarian ([Dirk Van Gorp, Radboud University Nijmegen](#)), all of whom worked with the ‘block grants’ and ‘pre-paid funds’ from the pilot – meaning that ‘their’ authors do not use the central submission system, but that their submissions get mediated by these third parties. All were very enthusiastic about the opportunity to use these block grants – and asserted that without their intermediary actions, most authors would not have known about this funding opportunity. The hurdles were similar for all three: there is need for a unified reporting system in the back-end and some red tape needs to be cut as the procedure has some very bureaucratic elements. In the discussion with the audience, two major publishers challenged both the ‘no hybrid’ rule and the 2000€ funding cap – both remarks being tackled by the official pilot

positions that there are enough quality OA journals who stay well below the 2000€ cap and that, as long as the double-dipping issue is not sufficiently addressed Europe-wide via offsetting deals, it makes no sense to support hybrid journals. A more justified critique by one of the audience members is that the Pilot raises the expectation of uninformed researchers that Open Access comes with a (high) publication charge for authors in any case. This does not do justice to the tons of initiatives where there are no author-facing processing charges – and it might put people off of the idea of Open Access all together. The Pilot has tried to tackle this issue by creating a separate activity around alternative funding models, as discussed below.

A second panel closed the morning session. This panel focused on alternative funding models and mechanisms for OA publishing platforms. Three participants in the [alternative funding workline of the pilot](#) presented their results: [Jadranka Stojanovski \(HRCÁK, Croatia\)](#), [Johanna Lilja \(FFLS\)](#) and [Inés Gil-Jaurena \(Open Praxis\)](#). While these initiatives mostly focused on the technical aspects of running an Open Access publishing platform, and how they used the Pilot funds to improve the quality of their platforms in order to offer a quality experience for authors – without them being charged article processing charges. One of the panel members even made the remark that they upgraded their entire system. The fourth panel member, [Saskia De Vries, talked about the Open Library of Humanities and the principles of FAIR open access](#) – an entirely different funding model for non-author facing APCs.

In the afternoon, Rob Johnson and Mattia Fosci from [Research Consulting](#) presented the report they created for the European Commission and OpenAIRE: [“Towards a Competitive and Sustainable OA Market in Europe”](#). In this report, Research Consulting investigated what would need to happen to reach immediate Open Access as default by 2020. It is very clear that at the current rate, this won't happen – and the report focuses on the roadblocks that prevent this. Due to the large diversity in the field of Open Access, one of the recommendations of the report is not to look for a silver bullet – but to take (sometimes small) practical steps towards more Open Access – acknowledging the pluralism of the publishing market. [Link to presentation](#)

In the breakout sessions that followed, the audience first got the opportunity to identify short-term opportunities, idealistic long-term goals and potential roadblocks along the six criteria the report has identified (author incentives and publisher incentives, monitoring and infrastructure, competition and pluralism) – and this for 4 distinctive areas: Gold APC-based OA, Gold non APC-based OA, Hybrid OA and Green OA. After half an hour of fun with stickers and group talk, the audience broke up in three groups, each discussing one area (Gold APC and hybrid were in one group). What comes out of this discussion will, among other sources of input, be used as the basis for the Roadmap that will eventually accompany the report.

Some highlights of the break-out sessions – by no means exhaustive. The results and write-up of this break-out session will be shared later under the form of a Roadmap:

- **Create a real marketplace for authors** – a big advantage of gold OA is authors have to make a choice. First criterion in journal selection is discipline, second is quality, but price sensitivity could become a third factor – then they will start to compare quality and price. A market could then bring down the prices. There is a beginning of price awareness. A related discussion **focused on efficiency vs author awareness**: in order to increase the total amount of OA publications, whether it's preferable to have very well informed researchers who arrange their own OA funding or to increase efficiency via transparent and standardised workflows on research administration level – where intermediary actors facilitate open access.

- **Reveal true figures/transparency of APC costs:** the lack of transparency and predictability in APC/BPC price setting is a big frustration for administrators.
- Improve visibility and research into **alternative business models** for publishers and platforms that work without author facing publishing charges. **Shift to added value of services** from publishers, rather than simply basing value of on copyright – there is also more research to alternative business models needed
- **Standardise publishing, grant processing and offsetting workflows** – this will make advocacy and monitoring much easier, will also provide statistical support for research
- ...

4.1.3 BEYOND APCs: ALTERNATIVE OPEN ACCESS PUBLISHING BUSINESS MODELS, The Hague, April 2018

Announcement and presentations: <https://www.openaire.eu/beyond-apcs-alternative-open-access-publishing-business-models>

Workshop report by Alexandra Jobmann: <https://oa2020-de.org/en/blog/2018/04/11/beyondapcs-openaire-workshop/>

Workshop report by Annica Wentzel : <http://openaccess.blogg.kb.se/2018/04/10/business-as-usual-or-not-openaire-workshop-about-alternative-publishing-models/>

4.2 Internal meetings

4.2.1 Alternative Funding Mechanism Workshop for APC-free Open Access journals (Dec 19th, KB, The Hague)

Full blogpost: <https://blogs.openaire.eu/?p=1701>

List of presentations delivered at the event

- Antti-Jussi Nygård, [Scientific Journals Online](#) – Federation of Finnish Learned Societies
- Dimitris Efstathiou, [EKT ePublishing](#) – National Documentation Centre/National Hellenic Research Foundation
- Drazenko Celjak, [Hrčak](#) – University of Zagreb Computing Centre (SRCE)
- Biljana Kosanović, [SCIndeks: The Serbian Citation Index](#) – Centre for Evaluation in Education and Science (CEON)
- Inés Gil-Jaurena, [Open Praxis](#) – International Council for Open and Distance Education
- Frédéric Dubois, [Internet Policy Review](#) – Alexander von Humboldt Institute for Internet and Society
- László Molnár, [Information Bulletin on Variable Stars](#) – Konkoly Observatory
- Laura Morvai, [Hungarian Educational Research Journal \(HERJ\)](#) – University of Debrecen

4.2.2 Internal workshop for Alternative Funding Mechanisms Second Call, The Hague, April 6 2018

- 9.00 – 10.30: Presentation of the bids supported by the 2nd call for alternative funding mechanisms
 - [Jean-Sébastien Caux, SciPost](#)
 - [Klaudia Grabowska, IBL PAN](#)
 - [Saskia De Vries and Johan Rooryck, FOAA](#)
 - [Sebastien Nordhoff, Language Science Press](#)
 - [Joe Deville, Julien McHardy, Janneke Adema, Vincent W.J. Van Gerven Oei: Mattering Press e.a.](#)
 - [James Smith, Open Library of Humanities](#)
- 10.30-11.30: Group discussion and lessons learnt from [Bid 1](#) and [Bid 2](#) (including coffee break)
- 11.30-13.00: Round tables: troubleshooting and in-depth sharing of knowledge and experiences
- 13.00-14.00: lunch and closing

4.3 Presentations

- Pablo de Castro, EC Gold OA Pilot Presentation at the CRISin Spring Conference in Oslo, April 21st 2015 https://www.slideshare.net/OpenAIRE_eu/ec-gold-oa-pilot-presentationoslo20150421
- Pablo de Castro, FP7 Post-Grant OA Pilot Open Access TAGE 2015 Zürich https://www.slideshare.net/OpenAIRE_eu/fp7-postgrant-oa-pilot-slides-open-access-tage-2015-zurich
- Pablo de Castro, FP7 post-grant OA publishing funds, OpenAIRE workshop, November 2015, Ghent https://www.slideshare.net/OpenAIRE_eu/fp7-postgrant-oa-publishing-funds-pablo-de-castro-openaire-workshop-ghent-nov2015
- Pablo de Castro, Evolving Strategies for Open Access Implementation: Some Findings from the OpenAIRE FP7 Post-Grant Open Access Pilot, Pubmet 2016, Zadar, Croatia https://www.slideshare.net/OpenAIRE_eu/evolving-strategies-for-open-access-implementation-some-findings-from-the-openaire-fp7-postgrant-open-access-pilot
- Pablo de Castro, The FP7 Post-Grant Open Access Pilot: An All-Encompassing Gold Open Access Funding Initiative, LIBER 2016, Helsinki https://www.slideshare.net/OpenAIRE_eu/the-fp7-postgrant-open-access-pilot-an-allencompassing-gold-open-access-funding-initiative
- Gwen Franck, Presentation at National Open Access event organized by EKT in Athens, Greece, June 2017 <http://www.ekt.gr/el/events/program/20876>
- Biljana Kosanovic "Open Science in Horizon 2020": the Serbia OpenAIRE National Workshop hosted by the University of Belgrade on November 8, 2016 <https://blogs.openaire.eu/?p=1611>
- Gwen Franck, Poster presentation at LIBER on July 6 2018 in Lille, France <https://liberconference.eu/programme/>
- Birgit Schmidt, Poster presentation at ELPUB 2018 in June 2018 in Toronto, Canada <https://elpub.episciences.org/4638>

4.4 Online training and webinars

- Pablo de Castro, Gold OA Pilot Webinar for OpenAIRE NOADs, May 15 2015 https://www.slideshare.net/OpenAIRE_eu/gold-oa-pilotwebinaropenaireoads20150519

- Pablo de Castro ; The EC/OpenAIRE FP7 Post-Grant Open Access Pilot: An Update for the South Region NOADs, July 28th, 2015, https://www.slideshare.net/OpenAIRE_eu/the-ecopenaire-fp7-postgrant-open-access-pilot-an-update-for-the-south-region-noads
- Pablo de Castro , The EC/OpenAIRE FP7 Post-Grant Open Access Pilot: An Update for the Nordic NOADs, August 27th 2015 https://www.slideshare.net/OpenAIRE_eu/the-ecopenaire-fp7-postgrant-open-access-pilot-an-update-for-the-nordic-noads
- Pablo de Castro ,The EC/OpenAIRE FP7 Post-Grant Open Access Pilot: A View on 'Region East', April 2016 <https://www.openaire.eu/fp7-post-grant-oa-publishing-funds-pilot-webinar-eastern-europe>
- Pablo de Castro , The Alternative Funding Mechanism for the EC FP7 Post-Grant Open Access Pilot, an update: March 18 2016 <https://www.openaire.eu/fp7-post-grant-open-access-publishing-funds-pilot-webinar-march-2016>
- Pablo de Castro , FP7 post-grant Open Access publishing funds pilot webinar (October 2015) https://www.slideshare.net/OpenAIRE_eu/fp7-postgrant-open-access-publishing-funds-pilot-webinar-october-2015
- Gwen Franck, FP7 Post-Grant Open Access Pilot webinar organized by Ghent University, June 13th, 2017
- Gwen Franck, OpenAIRE spring webinars: the FP7 Post-Grant Open Access Pilot , June 1st 2017 <https://www.openaire.eu/openaire-fp7-post-grant-open-access-pilot>
- Pablo de Castro, Webinar on the FP7 Post-Grant OA Pilot Implementation in the UK <https://blogs.openaire.eu/?p=683> : January 19, 2016 https://www.slideshare.net/OpenAIRE_eu/the-alternative-funding-mechanism-for-the-ec-fp7-postgrant-open-access-pilot
- Gwen Franck, The FP7 Post-Grant Open Access Pilot: explanation about extension period, May 11 and 15 - <https://www.openaire.eu/fp7-oapilot>
- Gwen Franck, The FP7 Post-Grant Open Access Pilot, October 23rd 2017 https://www.slideshare.net/OpenAIRE_eu/20171023-fp7-postgrant-open-access-pilot

4.5 Helpdesk

The Pilot Administration received 161 tickets through the OpenAIRE Helpdesk system. However, most questions about the Pilot have been received through the dedicated e-mailaddress provided by the Pilot (postgrantpilotinfo@openaire.eu) and through the personal e-mailaddresses of the Pilot administration.

4.6 Poster, infograph and fact sheets

- Fact sheet: <https://www.openaire.eu/openaire-factsheet-for-fp7-post-grant-open-access-pilot>
- Fact sheet translated in Serbian: https://h2020.rcub.bg.ac.rs/wp-content/uploads/2016/10/vodic_FP7PostGrant.pdf
- Infograph and poster are available via: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.998042>

FIGURE 3: POSTER OVERVIEW OF OPENAIRE2020 WP5 ACTIVITIES AS PRESENTED AT LIBER2018 AND ELPUB2018

5 | NON-AUTHOR FEE BASED FUNDING MECHANISM

5.1 First round: focus on technical improvements

Out of 17 applications, 11 initiatives have been funded, for a total of €200 000. The approved initiatives planned technical improvements on specific areas such as OpenAIRE compliance, providing article-level information to the [DOAJ](#), systematically collecting and exposing the funding information whenever it's made available by authors, producing XML versions of the published articles and implementing [ORCID](#) IDs. While almost all platforms worked on the above, some also ventured into data integration (for linking, reviewing, sharing and archiving), altmetrics, advanced statistical analysis and DOI integration. During a workshop in December 2016, all bidders got together to share experiences and provide mid-term reports. The table below is based on the final reports provided.

The detailed report of all 11 bids can be consulted [here](#). Contact details of the initiatives are available upon request.

- [Internet Policy Review](#) – Alexander von Humboldt Institute for Internet and Society (Germany). €16K
- [Annals of Geophysics](#) – Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia (Italy). €20K
- [Hrčak](#) – University of Zagreb Computing Centre (SRCE, Croatia). €28K
- [SCIIndeks: The Serbian Citation Index](#) – Centre for Evaluation in Education and Science (CEON, Serbia). €17K
- [Scientific Journals Online](#) – Federation of Finnish Learned Societies (Finland). €10K
- [Revistas CSIC](#) – Spanish National Research Council (Spain). €35K
- [Information Bulletin on Variable Stars](#) – Konkoly Observatory (Hungary). €14K
- [Open Praxis](#) – International Council for Open and Distance Education (Norway/Spain). €10.4K
- [EKT ePublishing](#) – National Documentation Centre/National Hellenic Research Foundation (Greece). €14.8K
- [Hungarian Educational Research Journal](#) (HERJ) – University of Debrecen (Hungary). €15K
- [International Journal of Digital Curation](#) (IJDC) – Digital Curation Centre (DCC, UK). €17.2K

These eleven bids provide a wide geographic coverage for the funding initiative. They also show a rather well-balanced distribution across European regions. The technical improvement plans included in the funded proposals make emphasis on specific areas such as OpenAIRE compliance, providing article-level information to the DOAJ, systematically collecting and exposing the funding information whenever it's made available by authors, producing XML versions of the published articles and implementing ORCID.

Moreover, the degree of overlapping across improvement plans offers clear opportunities for information exchange and eventual collaboration across proposals, and this is an aspect that the initiative will be keen to promote. An **email list** will be created for the purpose with all the funded stakeholders in it. This list will first be used to share the required details to formalize the funding agreement with OpenAIRE, and then for any potentially useful information to be shared across the funded stakeholders. A **workshop** to offer parties the opportunity to meet and discuss the work they've carried out by then is currently under consideration. This workshop, which would be held in The Hague towards the end of the year, would also provide a good opportunity for the project

coordination to do the mid-term progress assessment for the implementation of the improvement plans that is featured as part of the description of work for this funding initiative.

One specific workline that was not included in the original suggestions for technical improvements but that has frequently appeared on the collected work plans is **dissemination**. This area mainly applies to APC-free Open Access journal platforms that need to first explain the advantages offered by the proposed technical improvements to the editors of the journals they host. The opportunity to compare dissemination strategies across countries and initiatives and the results of their application is again a very interesting feature of this funding call.

Once the improvement plans are completed, short **case studies** will jointly be produced by the funded stakeholders and the FP7 Post-Grant OA Pilot describing the enhancement work that has been done with the support of OpenAIRE. These case studies may be released individually or be added as a whole to a report on opportunities for improving the APC-free Open Access publishing infrastructure in Europe. The final goal is that the work carried out under this initiative may eventually benefit all APC-free Open Access journal publishers, including particularly those who submitted bids that were not selected for funding.

5.2 Second round: focus on scalability and sustainability

With this second call, we wanted to acknowledge the efforts that are being made, within the OA publishing landscape, to develop, pilot, and apply business models other than author fee based ones. We wanted to support ongoing and new initiatives that put an effort in investigating or experimenting with sustainable and scalable alternative business models. We wanted to support both start-up initiatives during the planning and launching stages and/or publishing initiatives that want to transition from one business model to another. We also welcomed Research & Development initiatives, provided that the results will be made public and reusable.

The six initiatives that have been funded are the following:

- [Mattering Press](#): a consortium of 6 scholar-led open access book publishers will investigate how to transition away from charging book processing charges by developing a single platform for open access books that will experiment with alternative means of funding.
- [IBL PAN](#): The Institute of Literary Research of the Polish Academy of Sciences will design a sustainable open access business model for their journals, starting with a pilot for the most prominent journal in their portfolio 'Teksty Drugie'. This will happen in collaboration with the OpenEdition [revues.org](#) platform.
- [SciPost](#): The SciPost Foundation will implement its consortial funding model, recruit Fellows for its editorial colleges and create a portal template that will be reusable beyond the field of physics.
- [FAOO](#): support the 'flipping' of journals in Linguistics and Mathematics according to the Fair Open Access principles
- [Language Science Press](#): creation of a manual for community based open access publishing initiatives, together with the business data and business model – in order to provide an evidence-based business model canvas for start-up initiatives in linguistics and other disciplines

PUBLIC

- [Open Library of Humanities](#): OLH wants to solidify and scale-up their already successful business model, in order to ensure long-term sustainability by increasing the number of libraries and consortia participating

The initiatives that have received funding will conduct their work during the first half of 2018.

The results of their mid-term reporting are summarised in the presentations made during the April 2018 workshop:

- [Jean-Sébastien Caux, SciPost](#)
- [Klaudia Grabowska, IBL PAN](#)
- [Saskia De Vries and Johan Rooryck, FOAA](#)
- [Sebastien Nordhoff, Language Science Press](#)
- [Joe Deville, Julien McHardy, Janneke Adema, Vincent W.J. Van Gerven Oei: Mattering Press e.a.](#)
- [James Smith, Open Library of Humanities](#)

Results and reports will be published on the OpenAIRE blog and as a compiled document on Zenodo. As the reporting deadline for bids was put at July 15, 2018, these could not be added to this report yet.

Outputs already published:

- Open Library of Humanities: EmpowOA <https://blogs.openaire.eu/?p=2940>
- Language Science Press: Sebastian Nordhoff, Felix Kopecky. Full Disclosure: Open Business Data and the Publisher's Cookbook. ELPUB 2018, Jun 2018, Toronto, France. <[10.4000/proceedings.elpub.2018.8](https://doi.org/10.4000/proceedings.elpub.2018.8)>. <hal01816822>
- Language Science Press: final report: <https://blogs.openaire.eu/?p=3539>
- Mattering Press: "The prototype of our new pop up conference pack at #radicalOA2, featuring books from five OA publishers, including the 'book of books' usb device that allows our entire combined catalogue to be rapidly shared." (Twitter, @matteringpress, June 26th, 2018)
- Mattering Press: final report <https://blogs.openaire.eu/?p=3546>
- SciPost: Final report: <https://blogs.openaire.eu/?p=3556>

6 | FINAL CONCLUSIONS AND LESSONS LEARNT

This Pilot has proven that there is definitely a demand for funder-driven support for author fee payments. With over 800 FP7 projects making use of this Fund for in total more than 1300 publications over a period of 34 months, the Pilot has, after a slow start, gained traction. Thanks to targeted dissemination actions by the Pilot administration, open access publishers, library and repository managers and the OpenAIRE NOADs², this funding scheme has become widely known as a reliable source of funding to publish in Open Access, for the time it was in place.

Here lies the first ‘weakness’ of the Fund: as it became more widely known, the fact that the Pilot was limited in time and scope (FP7 projects, post-grant) led to some frustration by ineligible projects. The unwarranted expectation that this Pilot would transform into a **structural support mechanism** has been expressed by both beneficiaries and rejected applicants. The Pilot still receives requests for funding (via e-mail) by people unaware that this support is not a permanent service.

Perhaps surprisingly, the rule that the Pilot would not support hybrid journals was met with relatively little resistance. The Pilot administration has always taken great care explaining why it did not support this type of journals (as it did not want to support ‘double dipping’ using public funds) and usually applicants understood. Either because they did not know their journal of choice was hybrid, or because with certain funders this hybrid status is not an impediment for funding, this could lead to some sour reactions, but in general people understood after our explanation. We do believe that the ‘no-hybrid’ approach has proven its benefits, and it has definitely raised awareness among researchers about this issue. If anything, it shows the need **for more education on the different forms of open access publishing**, as in some cases journals and publishers remain deliberately unclear about their hybrid status (using terms like ‘author choice’ or ‘open access option’).

As the Pilot has experimented with pre-payment agreements for certain publishers and block grants for libraries, some lessons can be learnt from this experience as well. From the start, the Pilot has imposed firm conditions on the publishers involved about funding eligibility, including the application of a bulk discount for all publications processed via this system. However, the Pilot has been very accommodating when reporting was concerned, allowing different channels of evaluation (such as dashboards or spreadsheets) and timing of data delivery (sometimes at the moment of submissions, sometimes only when a publication was in its last editorial stage before publishing). This has on several occasions led to frustration on administration level and, more importantly, has made it difficult to conduct any interim reporting (an issue that has only now, at the final reporting stage, been fixed). The experience from this Pilot learns that, when entering into agreements with publishers, **a suitable and uniform reporting mechanism** has to be provided by the funder – ideally processing the data in a similar fashion and at the same time as individual submissions.

Another crucial element that proved to be difficult to execute well, was the rather **complicated invoicing procedure**. Invoices needed to be addressed to OpenAIRE (p/a Athena Research Centre) and could not contain VAT. No matter how many FAQs, information sheets and webinars delivered on the subject, the amount of submissions that got it ‘right’ from the first time were a minority. Invoices contained VAT, or were addressed to the researcher rather than to the OpenAIRE admin, or exceeded our funding caps. The bulk of the administrative effort consisted of fixing these errors,

² <https://www.openaire.eu/contact-noads>

often leading to tiresome back-and-forths between researchers, their administration, Pilot administration, the Pilot accounting office and the publishers issuing the invoices.

The fact that the Pilot administration and the Pilot accounting office were not located in the same institution proved to be an additional complicating factor, equally difficult to communicate. Similarly, the fact that the technical team supporting the Pilot website and the Pilot administration were not located in the same institution was problematic in the case of technical issues. Despite cordial relations between these different actors, having all of them **in the same institution** could have reduced a lot of frustration (or at least have simplified communication).

Finally, some remarks about the critique that this Pilot encourages the author fee based route in open access publishing. The Pilot has funded **17 non-author fee open access initiatives** in order for them to be able to solidify their activities both on a technical and a sustainability level.

Despite stressing that this Fund is indeed a ‘pilot’, of which all experiences – also the negative ones – should be taken into account when undertaking similar efforts in the future, some have reported that the mere existence of this Fund has led to an increase in author fee based publishing initiatives³. One can only hope that the **firm rules** set by this Pilot (the funding caps and the ‘no hybrid’ rules), have at least shown that it is possible to go about author fee based publishing in a non-predatory way. Several publishers have shown eagerness and willingness to collaborate with the conditions set by the Pilot, and expressed their availability to comply.

A detailed analysis of the dataset also shows that there is **space for negotiating** the actual author fees being charged. If this, on the one hand, might show that author fees are not inherently transparent and necessarily reflective of the real costs required to publish an article, on the other hand demonstrates **that rules sets by funders have a real impact on the publishing market, which can be influenced in favor of researchers and institutions, despite the perception of a completely inelastic market dominated only by major players.**

³ See for example https://www.slideshare.net/OpenAIRE_eu/openaire-workshop-beyond-apcs-jadranka-stojanovski slide 16

7 | FULL LIST OF MILESTONES AND DELIVERABLES

D5.1 Article policy/specifications guidelines - UCL) Report
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1304856>

D5.2 First periodic report on APC uptake and metrics (LIBER) Report

D5.3 Market/Economic impact study– (LIBER) Report <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.401029>

D5.4 Second periodic report on APC uptake and metrics– (LIBER) Report
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1291912>

D5.5 Roadmap for a sustainable and competitive market for open access publishing – (LIBER) Report <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1304904>

D5.6 FP7 Post-Grant Open Access Pilot, Final Report 13 – (LIBER) Report
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1304908>

MS1 APCs workflow mapping – (UCL) Report

MS2 Launch of APC pilot – (LIBER) System Running

MS3 Information packs for NOADs and publisher – (LIBER) Information on the OpenAIRE portal <https://www.openaire.eu/postgrantoapilot>

MS34 Assessment of uptake and priority check – (LIBER) Internal report Various posts published on <https://blogs.openaire.eu/?cat=44>

MS49 Workshop on sustainable open access publishing – (LIBER) Public recording and onepage report <https://blogs.openaire.eu/?p=1884>

MS72 Third reporting on APC uptake and metrics – (LIBER) Interim report published in the web <https://blogs.openaire.eu/?p=1801>

MS73 Final reporting on APC uptake and metrics – (LIBER) Interim report published in the web <https://blogs.openaire.eu/?p=2917>